

Johannes Ciconia

Quod jactatur

partitura

revisione
Luca Bianchini

Quod jactatur

Johannes Ciconia

Edited by

Luca Bianchini

ItalianOpera · 2026

www.italianopera.org

About this edition.

The present edition provides a realization of Johannes Ciconia's enigmatic canon *Quod jactatur*, transmitted in the Modena manuscript MOe.5.24, f. 21v. The reconstruction is based on the interpretation developed in the accompanying study, where the canon is interpreted through the application of the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System. According to this solution, the piece is not a continuously simultaneous three-voice canon, but a circular structure organized into seven blocks of five *tempora*. The *contra* acts as the generative voice, while *triplum* and *tenor* alternate active sections with structural silences. These silences are not editorial omissions, but part of the mechanism required by the canon construction and by its enigmatic motto.

A detailed discussion of the manuscript, the analytical method, and the reasoning underlying this reconstruction is available in the accompanying study:

Luca Bianchini, *Quod jactatur: A Proposed Solution through the Pythagorean 1–3–5 Inverse System*. Published on Zenodo, 2026. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20582482

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Suggested Citation

Johannes Ciconia, *Quod jactatur*, edited by Luca Bianchini. ItalianOpera, 2026.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20582482](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20582482)

The score begins on the following page.

Quod Jactatur

Johannes Ciconia

Canon

Realization by Luca Bianchini

Triplum

Contra

Tenor

6

11

16

21

Musical score for measures 21-25. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 21: Treble has a quarter note G4, eighth rest, eighth G4; Middle has quarter notes G4, A4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 22: Treble has quarter notes A4, B4; Middle has a half note G4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 23: Treble has a half note G4; Middle has a quarter rest, quarter note G4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 24: Treble has eighth rest, eighth G4, eighth rest, eighth Bb4; Middle has eighth notes G4, A4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 25: Treble has quarter notes G4, A4; Middle has quarter notes G4, A4; Bass has a whole rest.

26

Musical score for measures 26-30. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 26: Treble has quarter notes Gb4, A4; Middle has eighth notes Gb4, A4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 27: Treble has quarter notes Bb4, A4; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 28: Treble has a quarter rest, quarter note Gb4; Middle has a half note Gb4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 29: Treble has eighth notes Gb4, A4; Middle has eighth notes Gb4, A4; Bass has a whole rest. Measure 30: Treble has quarter notes Gb4, A4, Bb4; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4; Bass has a whole rest.

31

Musical score for measures 31-35. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 31: Treble has a quarter note Gb4, quarter rest; Middle has eighth notes Gb4, A4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4. Measure 32: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4. Measure 33: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has a quarter rest, quarter note Gb4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4. Measure 34: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has eighth notes Gb4, A4; Bass has a half note Gb4. Measure 35: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4, Bb4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4.

36

Musical score for measures 36-40. The system consists of three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. Measure 36: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4; Bass has a half note Gb4. Measure 37: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4, Bb4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4. Measure 38: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4. Measure 39: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has a quarter rest, quarter note Gb4; Bass has eighth notes Gb4, A4. Measure 40: Treble has a whole rest; Middle has quarter notes Gb4, A4, Bb4; Bass has quarter notes Gb4, A4.

41

Musical score for measures 41-45. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. The key signature has one flat (B-flat). The time signature is 4/4. The music features a mix of eighth and quarter notes, with some rests and ties. Measure 41 starts with a quarter note G4, followed by a quarter note A4, and a quarter note Bb4. Measure 42 has a quarter note C5, a quarter note D5, and a quarter note E5. Measure 43 has a quarter note F5, a quarter note G5, and a quarter note A5. Measure 44 has a quarter note Bb5, a quarter note C6, and a quarter note D6. Measure 45 has a quarter note E6, a quarter note F6, and a quarter note G6.

46

Musical score for measures 46-50. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. The key signature has one flat (B-flat). The time signature is 4/4. The music continues with eighth and quarter notes. Measure 46 has a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a quarter note Bb4. Measure 47 has a quarter note C5, a quarter note D5, and a quarter note E5. Measure 48 has a quarter note F5, a quarter note G5, and a quarter note A5. Measure 49 has a quarter note Bb5, a quarter note C6, and a quarter note D6. Measure 50 has a quarter note E6, a quarter note F6, and a quarter note G6.

51

Musical score for measures 51-55. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. The key signature has one flat (B-flat). The time signature is 4/4. The music continues with eighth and quarter notes. Measure 51 has a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a quarter note Bb4. Measure 52 has a quarter note C5, a quarter note D5, and a quarter note E5. Measure 53 has a quarter note F5, a quarter note G5, and a quarter note A5. Measure 54 has a quarter note Bb5, a quarter note C6, and a quarter note D6. Measure 55 has a quarter note E6, a quarter note F6, and a quarter note G6.

56

Musical score for measures 56-60. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Middle, and Bass. The key signature has one flat (B-flat). The time signature is 4/4. The music continues with eighth and quarter notes. Measure 56 has a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a quarter note Bb4. Measure 57 has a quarter note C5, a quarter note D5, and a quarter note E5. Measure 58 has a quarter note F5, a quarter note G5, and a quarter note A5. Measure 59 has a quarter note Bb5, a quarter note C6, and a quarter note D6. Measure 60 has a quarter note E6, a quarter note F6, and a quarter note G6.

